

1 **EMT and polarity-associated transcriptional processes active during lineage commitment in the**
2 **human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here changes in EMT
9 and polarity-associated transcriptional processes during lineage commitment in the human embryo. This
10 included changes in vimentin, BBS9, and PRICKLE4.

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